

APPRAISAL OF LEARNING BEYOND CLASSROOMS IN INDIA - AN INQUIRY INTO THE STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Learning beyond classrooms has emerged as a key dimension to education in India, supplementing formal instructional, technology-enabled approach. It represents a shift from rote-based, exam-centric education towards holistic and experiential modes of knowledge acquisition. This paper attempts to critically evaluate the strengths and challenges of such learning in Indian setting. It looks at how extra-curricular activities, digital platforms, vocational training, and community engagement help foster holistic development, creating employability skills, and prominently civic responsibility, in alignment with the vision of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. In the same breath, it also delves into persistent challenges that limit its equitable reach and effectiveness such as digital divide, exam-centric approach, insufficient to poor infrastructure, and socio-cultural barriers. The analysis projects that while learning beyond classrooms holds transformative potential for democratizing and decentralising knowledge and preparing youth for 21st-century challenges, system-induced reforms and broad-based inclusive strategies are essential to ensure its sustainability and impact. The effectiveness of Learning beyond classrooms depends largely on addressing structural inequalities and integrating these practices within the broader educational framework.

Keywords: *Experiential learning, NEP 2020, Digital divide, Holistic education, Skill development*

Introduction

Learning is not a four walled classroom experience but a continuous and multidimensional process involving experiences, interactions, and exposures beyond formal education. In India,

traditional classroom pedagogy has been the norm since independence but learning beyond classrooms, through extracurricular activities, community engagement, digital platforms and, skill-based programs is gaining ground in recent times and has gained renewed importance. This trend is closely in tune with the vision of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, which emphasizes holistic, multidisciplinary, and experiential learning. Learning beyond classrooms through community engagement, experiential practices, digital platforms, co-curricular activities, and vocational training has emerged as a crucial complement to formal education. Beyond classroom experiences, such as internships, cultural exchange, or online courses, reshape how learners acquire knowledge and prepare for the complexities of modern life. Despite its vision and potential, learning beyond classrooms in India faces many structural, operational and socio-cultural challenges. An appraisal of learning beyond classrooms in India requires a balanced inquiry into both its strengths and opportunities. This paper seeks to understand the transformative potential of learning beyond classrooms and also identify the gaps to be addressed to make it sustainable and inclusive part of India's education system.

Strengths

1. Holistic Development

Traditional classroom learning in India has long emphasized academic achievement measured in ranks and grades. Education fundamentally focus on the all-round development. Learning beyond classrooms helps nurture holistic growth by addressing cognitive, emotional, social, physical, and ethical dimensions of education. Debate, art, sports, and project-based learning stimulate critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. Community learning programs like NSS, NCC, and youth clubs inculcate values of social responsibility, volunteerism, and respect for diversity. Schools and higher education institutions must integrate extracurricular achievements into formal curricula and assessments, invest in infrastructure, and adopt learner-centred pedagogies.

2. Integration of Technology and Digital Platforms

The integration of technology has been a boon for learning beyond classrooms in India. With the rise of digital platforms, mobile applications, and e-learning ecosystems, allow learners to access knowledge anytime and anywhere. Platforms like SWAYAM, DIKSHA, e-Pathshala, and NPTEL have expanded access to high-quality educational resources. Similarly, private EdTech platforms have created new opportunities for personalized and flexible learning. The EdTech has created a situation where attending the college is more of a formality to fulfil the needs of admission and examination. All the learning can be had outside the classroom. Online

courses, coding boot camps, and MOOCs enable students to acquire knowledge and skills beyond prescribed curricula at their time and leisure. MOOCs has changed the dimension of learning beyond the classrooms. Recorded lectures, open educational resources, and interactive content make learning possible to those outside the formal schooling. Digital platforms help skill development and employability, aligning with India's vision of a knowledge-based economy.

3. Community and Experiential Learning

Community and experiential learning enables students to connect academic knowledge with real-world situations. These approaches provide transformative opportunities for hands-on experience, social responsibility, and practical skill development. It encourage students to engage with society and contribute. The **National Service Scheme (NSS)**, **National Cadet Corps (NCC)** expose learners to activities like health awareness, environmental conservation, literacy, and disaster relief work. The experiences cultivate values like empathy, teamwork, leadership, and civic consciousness, vital for building a participatory democracy. Experiential learning emphasizes "learning by doing." Field visits, internships, apprenticeships, and project-based assignments allow learners to apply classroom concepts in practical situations. It enhances employability by linking education to practical skills and strengthens social responsibility and ethical awareness.

4. Skill Development for Employability

Learning beyond Classrooms Bridge the gap between education and employability. Traditional classroom instruction is theoretical, leaving students underprepared for the demands of a rapidly changing needs of the industry and market. Beyond-classroom initiatives provide practical, industry-relevant skills that enhance both career readiness and lifelong learning capacities. Skill India Mission **and** Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) promote hands-on vocational training in areas like IT, retail, healthcare, and manufacturing. Apprenticeship programs and industry partnerships enable students to gain real-world exposure. With the rise of EdTech platforms, students acquire future-oriented skills. Incubation centres, start-up competitions, and maker-spaces in universities encourage students to experiment, innovate, and develop entrepreneurial minds. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes vocational education, multidisciplinary learning, and integration of employability skills into mainstream curricula. Hands on experience is critical for learning beyond the classroom.

5. Inclusivity and Cultural Learning

Learning beyond classrooms in India is not all about skill development and digital exposure but about fostering inclusivity and cultural awareness. Informal, community-based learning spaces like local festivals, folk traditions, storytelling, theatre, and art encourage students to get exposed to diverse cultural practices. It helps preserve indigenous knowledge systems which nurturing respect for pluralism, tolerance, and social harmony. From an inclusive point of view, beyond-classroom learning offers opportunities for learners from different social, linguistic, and regional backgrounds to learn from each other which traditional classrooms may not allow. Peer-to-peer learning helps overcome rigid hierarchies of the classroom and liberate knowledge from dogmas.

Challenges

1. Digital Divide and Inequality

The learning beyond classrooms in India is deeply dependent on technology through online courses, EdTech platforms, virtual classrooms, and digital resources. However, the digital divide remains a primary barrier to equitable access where majority of rural and marginalized learners suffer from poor connectivity, and unaffordable technology unlike the urban pockets. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the stark reality in which many government school students lacked access to smartphones or reliable electricity. Low-income families were disproportionately affected. Digital learning often looks like reinforcing existing socio-economic divides. Investment in rural digital infrastructure, localized multilingual content, and training programs to enhance digital literacy needs to be focussed to realise the goals.

2. Societal and Institutional Mind-sets

The Indian education system has traditionally been exam-oriented, where grades and ranks are a benchmark. This reduces non-classroom learning such as sports, arts, community service, vocational training, and digital skill-building as non-essential. At the societal level, parents and communities offer limited encouragement for children to pursue extracurricular activities or experiential learning opportunities where time spent outside the classroom is viewed as a distraction. A paradigm shift is needed to overcome this mind-set. It requires redefining success in education to value creativity, problem-solving, sensitizing parents and communities and recognizing extracurricular and non-classroom achievements in evaluation and career.

3. Lack of Infrastructure and Policy Implementation

Learning beyond classrooms in India, is crippled by infrastructural and policy implementation issues. Libraries, laboratories, playgrounds, or community learning spaces are essential for

experiential and skill-based education but many government schools lack basic facilities and those with basic facilities are poorly utilized due to shortage of trained staff. Budgetary constraints, bureaucratic delays, and fragmented coordination between central and state governments pose serious challenges. Addressing these gaps requires fair public investment in school infrastructure, accountability mechanisms for implementation, partnerships with civil society organizations and the private sector, and prominently, continuous monitoring and evaluation.

4. Quality and Credibility

The expansion of learning beyond classrooms in India has created new opportunities for holistic education but the question of quality and credibility remains. Proliferation of EdTech platforms with unverified content quality, teaching methods, and evaluation makes it difficult to ensure meaningful learning outcomes. The significant social media presence, publicity and aggressive marketing strategies exploit parental anxieties. The challenge of credibility is compounded by the absence of formal recognition for beyond-classroom learning in India's assessment frameworks. Ensuring quality and credibility requires regulation and accreditation of EdTech and skill development programs, standardized frameworks for assessment and certification bench marks, and continuous monitoring and feedback mechanisms to maintain accountability

5. Cultural and Gender Barriers

In rural and semi-urban areas, girls face mobility concerns due to safety, household responsibilities, or conservative attitudes. Participation in extracurricular activities is often discouraged, stereotyping traditional gender roles. Lack of gender-sensitive infrastructure, safe transport, contributes to lower confidence levels and limits exposure to diverse learning experiences for girls. Caste, class, regional identities, and linguistic barriers in digital platforms and extracurricular programs exclude students who are not fluent in English or dominant regional languages. The solution lies in promoting gender-sensitive infrastructure and policies, reshaping community mind-sets, and integrating local cultural knowledge and practices into formal education,

Learning beyond classrooms in India presents huge potential to democratize and decentralise education. In the changing face of the 21st century job and industry concerns and requirements, it prepares students for real-world challenges. The NEP 2020 was a step in this direction inculcating equity, inclusivity, and quality as part of a broader vision of learning beyond classrooms. However, a lot needs to be done. Strengthening digital infrastructure in rural areas,

Teacher-training to integrate classroom and beyond-classroom pedagogies, recognizing vocational skills as legitimate components of assessment and changing the parental and societal mind set towards non-traditional learning helps bridge the gap.

Concluding Observations

Learning beyond classrooms in India is a transformative move away from a narrow exam-centric framework towards holistic, experiential, and inclusive learning. It offers a new perspective to understand and evaluate education. It opens up new opportunities for students to acquire critical life skills, employable competencies, and civic engagement which are largely overlooked within conventional classrooms. The advent of digital platforms, community-based initiatives, vocational training, and extracurricular focus represents the huge potential of Learning beyond classrooms. However, this potential is limited by an array of challenges. The digital divide, complex and rigid societal and institutional mind-sets, insufficient infrastructure, and gaps in policy formulation and implementation, concerns over quality and credibility, and deep-seated cultural and gender barriers are just a few to name. The way forward requires a multi-dimensional strategy involving investment in infrastructure, bridging digital inequalities, regulation of EdTech and vocational training, and recognition of extracurricular achievements. Prominently, a paradigm shift in social attitudes is needed where parents, educators, and institutions value and trust learning as a multi-dimensional, skill-acquiring process rather than a tool for grades and ranks. Balanced and an integrated classroom and beyond-classroom learning will shape an education system that is inclusive, innovative, community-driven and future-ready.

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